

Carbonite Coffin for ConedaKOR: A database software with a built-in self-degradable static mode as a sustainable Digital Humanities research infrastructure

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Since the early days of Digital Humanities, data collections stored in online databases have been a common, yet controversial scholarly output format. This is because their innovative potential for research is countered by preservation issues (Unsworth 2000, Cohen/Rosenzweig 2006). The sustainability of complex digital resources, particularly web-based information systems, has recently emerged as a key topic in DH research (Meneses/Furuta 2019, Miller/Taylor-Poleskey 2020, Tucker 2022, VandeCreek 2024). In the following use-case, the long-term provision is directly addressed in the software design. The proposed solution is a controlled transformation, or “graceful degradation” (Nowviskie/Porter 2009), implemented as a software feature to create a static site. This approach enables the software to adapt to changing circumstances, such as the end of a research project, without compromising the integrity of the data.

ConedaKOR is a web-based database system for cultural heritage objects that has been developed in collaboration with multiple research projects since 2009 (Schepp et al. 2023). It incorporates various DH trends: a knowledge graph data model, API-based services, etc. The introduction of a software-as-a-service-model within DARIAH-DE was an important step towards easier operation. Experience has shown that, for research projects with limited resources, sustainably operating a powerful database system poses a major challenge. A common curation measure for legacy websites is to create static versions, typically using web crawlers. As we consider the static stage to be integral to the life cycle, ConedaKOR now features an integrated static mode that allows for seamless conversion without compromising data, content, or user experience.¹

¹ Latest static version: <https://github.com/coneda/kor/tree/static>.

The Text Database and Dictionary of Classic Mayan uses ConedaKOR to manage its extensive image collection, which is freely available through the “Maya Image Archive”.² The database has been built and maintained for several years as part of a long-term programme of the German Academies of Sciences and Humanities. As with any long-running research project, it will eventually reach an end-of-life phase: no new material will be added and staff and funding will be reduced. During this phase, a static mode would enable the archive to remain online with minimal maintenance costs.

ConedaKOR has separate layers for data (server-based backend) and interface (client-based frontend). Built on this “API-first approach”, the static environment could be implemented by saving JSON-responses to JSON-files, which the frontend could then load instead of the JSON-API (Fig 1.). In static mode the client has to run the search workload. To enable this, we used a small summary JSON-file containing only the searchable data. Tests with clients demonstrated remarkable speed and overall performance even on mobile devices. Complex database systems typically have extensive rights management, which cannot be provided in static websites. Therefore, the static build is created from the viewpoint of a specific user and their permissions. This enables rights-based selection of publishable content and/or multiple environments. APIs such as ConedaKOR’s OAI-PMH are unavailable in static mode but are dispensable if harvesting is performed prior to entering static mode. A static, server-hosted website that leverages client-side browser capabilities can strike the right balance between offering easy, low-barrier access to complex data collections and remaining a persistent, trustworthy and citable resource.

This leads to a time-saving maintenance, cost-efficient data provision and reduced consumption of environmental resources. Integrating a static degradation into the software development phase shifts curation resources into the project’s funding period. It enables compliance with the “Endings Principles for Digital Longevity” (Huculak/Davis 2025) without foregoing important functions at the height of the project. In summary, this approach considers several facets of sustainability, as described by Tucker (2022): technological, financial, environmental, and “human” aspects. Furthermore, a key feature of this “carbonite coffin” is its reversibility. Once financial and personal resources are available again, the full application can be rebuilt from its static conversion.

² Maya Image Archive: <https://classicmayan.kor.de.dariah.eu>.

Figure 1: Overview of the final structure.

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